

Bengal), Bihar, and Andhra Pradesh. Mean grain yield over 5 locations was 4.4 t/ha and was more than that of check variety Tilakkachari (2.9 t/ha). At Arundhutinagar, it yielded around 6 t/ha. The water level varied from 40 to 70 cm in

the test locations (Table 1).

CN505-5-32-9 is photoperiod sensitive and flowers the first week of Nov when day length is 11 h 50 min. It has stiff culms and moderate elongation capacity, and is 110 cm tall when grown in shallow

water, but can elongate to 138 cm in deep water (Table 2).

CN505-5-32-9 produces 250 panicles/m² and long bold, white grains. The 1,000-grain weight is 24.8 g. It is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and brown spot. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing rice variety for irrigated lands

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Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing, dwarf (93 cm) rice variety was released recently in U. P. for cultivation in irrigated fields. It was developed in Sri Lanka from the cross IR262/Remadja and tested in the International Rice Observational Nursery as BG90-2 in 1974. The plants have good tillering capacity, mature in 126-132 d, and have high yield potential. Grains are long, slender, and translucent, with good cooking quality. It is moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya, which has become susceptible.

Pant Dhan 4 was tested in station trials from 1976 to 1980 and in state variety trials from 1979 to 1982 (see table). □

Performance of Pant Dhan 4 in state variety trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial centers	Grain yield (t/ha)		CD at 5%	CV in 5%	Days to maturity	
	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya			Pant Dhan 4	Jaya
<i>1981 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	4.6	4.6	0.1	1.8	134	131
Bareilly	7.0	6.7	0.2	2.1	133	141
Haldwani	7.2	5.4	1.2	12.4	139	143
Hardoi	4.1	4.3	0.2	4.3	124	135
Mathura	5.1	4.8	0.3	4.5	123	130
Meerut	2.0	1.7	0.3	12.6	140	141
Jhansi	2.1	2.5	0.6	16.1	123	127
Barabanki	3.2	3.6	0.4	7.9	122	129
Etawah	3.1	4.3	1.0	20.6	122	126
Varanasi	3.1	3.5	1.5	12.0	110	126
Average	4.2	4.2	—	—	126	133
<i>1982 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	3.8	4.5	0.09	1.73	131	133
Bareilly	5.9	5.6	0.07	0.75	132	139
Haldwani	5.8	5.5	0.9	9.8	152	154
Hardoi	4.8	4.7	0.3	5.3	130	138
Mathura	4.3	4.6	0.2	3.2	115	128
Meerut	6.3	4.5	1.0	10.8	139	139
Jhansi	5.6	4.7	N.S.	22.2	129	137
Barabanki	—	—	—	—	—	—
Etawah	—	—	—	—	—	—
Varanasi	—	—	—	—	—	—
Average	5.2	4.9	—	—	132	138

Variation of ripening periods among rice genotypes

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Most of the photosynthates accumulated as grain yield are formed from anthesis to senescence. Little information is available on the extent of variation in this duration. We sought to define ripening period for rice genotypes with a wide range of maturity duration. The entries were from

Vegetative and grain ripening periods in days for different rice types, Almora, India.

Duration	Genotypes (no.)	Duration (d)			
		Preanthesis		Postanthesis	
		Mean	Range	Mean	Range
Short	20	80	65-87	37	20-43
Medium	45	96	88-105	36	30-44
Medium-long	22	100	106-114	40	33-48
Long	4	120	115-125	37	28-45

different rice growing regions and included some local hill collections. Entries were transplanted in irrigated fields on 15

Jul 1981 and 1982 at Almora, at 1,600 m above sea level. Of an initial 100 entries, 9 were dropped because they did not